

INCREASING THE INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS OF THE REGION AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article expresses an opinion about the role of investment activity in sustainable economic development, the directions of development of investment activity and increasing the attractiveness of the investment environment.

Key words: investments, investment attractiveness, stimulation of investment activity, infrastructure development.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev to the Oliy Majlis: "World experience shows that any country that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. That's why investment is the driver of the economy, it is no exaggeration to say that it is the heart of the economy in Uzbek terms. We will achieve rapid development of our economy only by actively attracting investments and launching new production facilities. Positive results in the economy make it possible to systematically solve the accumulated problems in the social sphere. We must all understand this deeply and organize our work on this basis. In order to widely attract foreign investments, it is necessary to take measures to fully demonstrate the investment potential of our country, which should be one of the most urgent issues in our daily life" [1], noting that foreign investments are extremely important in the development of the economy. recognizes the importance and relevance of its involvement. A number of measures aimed at increasing the investment attractiveness of our country's economy and improving the system of effective use of the existing investment potential are the measures of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "Measures to further improve the mechanisms of attracting foreign direct investment to the economy of the Republic "Resolution No. PQ-4300 on the activities of priority is given to tasks related to information about opportunities and potential [2].

Factors determining the attractiveness of foreign investment in regions can be divided into five groups:

1. Market factors (domestic market and export opportunities).
2. Availability of rich natural resources.
3. Production cost factors.
4. Investment environment.
5. The country's economic development strategy [3]

A well-thought-out investment policy is of great importance in ensuring the rapid pace of economic development and maintaining macroeconomic stability in our republic. After all, investments, as an important factor of economic development, provide modernization of production, technical and technological updates and innovation, creation of new jobs and increase of income of enterprises. How important the issue is can be seen from the investment policy aimed at regularly increasing investment flows over the years. Indeed, in recent years, the scope of measures aimed at increasing the volume of investments has been significantly increased both legally and practically. Especially as a result of active investment policy, positive growth in the dynamics of investment flow is observed in our republic (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The volume of capital investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2023, trillion. sum[4]

In 2023, the volume of capital investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 352.1 trillion soums. Increasing the investment attractiveness of the region is of great importance for sustainable economic development and is seen as an important factor in this process. Investments are considered as the most important resource in the economic development of the region. Investments will increase the development of infrastructure, strengthen the industrial sector with the introduction of new technologies, stimulate innovation and create new jobs.

There are main directions for increasing investment attractiveness:

1. Promotion of investments by the state. In order to increase investments, state and regional authorities should pay attention to such guidelines as legislation, financial deductions in the tax field, and improvement of investment acceptance conditions. At the same time, it is important to provide indicators of the state in the selection of developing sectors and projects worthy of investment in order to increase investments.

2. Infrastructure development. Investments play an important role in infrastructure development. The development of roads, railways, electricity, water supply and other infrastructure will increase travel, innovation and sales of industrial products.

3. Application of technologies and introduction of innovations. Investments facilitate the introduction of new technologies and innovations. Thanks to new technologies and innovations in the industry, it is possible to improve product quality and make production processes more efficient.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to ensure the practical implementation of the following tasks in order to improve the system of attracting foreign investments to the economy and their effective use:

- formation of software platforms aimed at state insurance of investors' investments, assessment of existing conditions and possibilities of attracting foreign investments in the regions;

- improving the regulatory framework for attracting investments to the regions and providing tax preferences for their development, wide incentives for increasing the share of tax revenues remaining in the region;

- to ensure the practical implementation of the tasks of restructuring the internal structure of industrial sectors, directing foreign investments to the production of industrial products and advanced technologies for the production of high-quality industrial goods;

- use of various models of legal regulation methods for state support of investment activities, formation of digital investment services system in the unification of legislation on investment activities;

- use of the public-private partnership mechanism that provides international technology transfer for investment projects, optimization of the effective project risk management system when introducing an integrated system of investment project management, etc.

List of used literature:

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